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**SYNERGISTIC ENHANCEMENT OF TEXTILE DYE WASTEWATER
TREATMENT VIA ELECTROCOAGULATION COUPLED WITH
Tamarindus indica NATURAL POLYMER**

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This study evaluates the synergistic treatment of textile dye wastewater using electrocoagulation (EC) integrated with a locally available natural polymer, *Tamarindus indica* seed powder. Industrial dye wastewater with an initial Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) of 2097 mg/L, pH 7.12, and electrical conductivity of 7.88 mS/cm (color concentration assumed as 1000 ppm for evaluation) was used to assess performance. Electrocoagulation was performed using aluminium (Al), ductile iron (Fe), and stainless steel (SS) electrodes. Among these, the aluminium anode and stainless-steel cathode (Al/SS) configuration achieved the best performance, with 72.4% COD and 92.8% color removal at an optimal charge loading of 800 C/L. The process increased pH from 7.12 to 8.29 and reduced conductivity from 7.88 to 6.81 mS/cm, indicating effective coagulation and pollutant destabilization. Further enhancement in COD and color removal was achieved by coupling the optimized EC system with *Tamarindus indica* seed powder (10 mg/L). Compared to EC alone, COD reduction improved from 72.4% to 88.3% and color removal from 92.8% to 98.8%. The final pH decreased to 6.4, reflecting the mild acidity of the polymer that enhanced floc formation. This hybrid EC-polymer process is cost-effective as it reduces chemical consumption, sludge generation, and overall operational costs through the use of locally available, biodegradable coagulants. The developed method demonstrates strong potential for sustainable, economical, and environmentally friendly industrial-scale dye wastewater treatment.

Keywords: Textile dye wastewater, Electrocoagulation, *Tamarindus indica*, Aluminium electrode, Natural polymer